

PREPARATION OF POLY-(LACTIC ACID) SCAFFOLDS REINFORCED WITH BACTERIAL CELLULOSE NANOFIBRES

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SUMMARY

Bacterial-cellulose (BC) nano-fibres were used to reinforce poly-(lactic acid) (PLA) composites. The wettability between water and PLA is improved by BC addition. Also, a more interconnected porous structure for such composites is obtained. The new composites have potential for use in tissue engineering as a scaffold material with good cell attachment, coupled with improved mechanical properties.

Keywords: bacterial cellulose, nano-fibre, poly-lactic acid, freeze drying, scaffold

INTRODUCTION

Biopolymers are often used as biomaterials in tissue engineering, for example for tissue replacement and for organ transplantation. Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) is one of the few synthetic biodegradable biopolymers, and is widely used for manufacture of biodegradable tissue engineering scaffolds due to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, good mechanical properties and processability. PLA also has been used as an FDA-approved biopolymer for clinical use, such as in the manufacture of surgical sutures [1]. However, poor hydrophilicity and the lack of natural recognition sites on the PLA surface are not ideal for cell adhesion to the substrate, which is the critical step for cell spreading, migration and differentiation [2]. Many approaches, such as plasma treatment [3], entrapment of a second functional polymer with the surface [4], and partial surface hydrolysis by both acid [5] and base treatment [6], have been applied for surface modification of the preformed PLA samples. Some disadvantages still remain. For example, diffusion is difficult with plasma treatment of thick samples, and the 3D structure will collapse for solvent dilution of the surface and the bulk structure. We show that the use of nano-sized hydrophilic bacterial cellulose fibres, added using acid hydrolysis, improves the cell attachment of PLA-based composites.

Bacterial cellulose, which is cultured from strains of acetobacter xylinum, has unique properties including high water holding capacity, high crystallinity, a fine fibre network, and high tensile strength [7-11]. The elastic modulus of bacterial cellulose samples with diameters ranging from 27-88 nm was measured to be 78 ± 17 G Pa [11]. Bacterial cellulose has gained attention in biomedical applications such as in the development of artificial skin and blood vessels, due to its biodegradability, biocompatibility and

biological affinity [12-13]. Like nano-cellulose isolated from plant fibre, the use of rigid BC nano-fibres improves the mechanical properties of low solution concentration PLA scaffolds that are otherwise too weak to be used even with high porosity [14]. PLA-based composites with BC nano-fibres, and featuring a 3D porous structure, were produced by thermal-induced liquid-solid phase separation (TIPS) technology, which can produce a porous structure with high porosity and good mechanical properties [15]. The porous structures were prepared by solution casting the PLA with 1, 4 dioxane solution, followed by freeze-drying. The microstructure and water absorption of the resulting PLA and composite were characterized.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The bacterial cellulose pellicles were kindly provided by Tianjin University, China. The gel-like pellicles were washed in running water for one day and then boiled in a 1% (w/w) aqueous solution of NaOH for 4 hr to remove bacterial cell debris. Then, the pellicles were again washed free of alkali in running water. BC nano-fibres were prepared by acid hydrolysis in 50 wt. % sulphuric acid, heated at 55 °C for 4 hr with continuous stirring. After completion of the hydrolysis, the flask was dipped in a bath of ice-cold water to stop the hydrolysis. The aqueous suspension of nano-fibres was diluted and repeatedly washed using centrifugation. The BC crystals were collected by freeze-drying of the aqueous suspension.

PLA/1,4-dioxane solution was heated at 60°C until a clear solution was observed. The uniformly dispersed nano-fibres and PLA/1,4-dioxane mixture was placed in a beaker and quickly frozen in a fridge for 2 hr. A porous structure with different morphology can be obtained by freeze-drying the frozen samples at -80 °C for 12 hr under a vacuum of about 0.60 mbar.

The bacterial cellulose nano-fibre samples were examined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Philips CM 200, NL). A droplet of the diluted suspension was allowed to float on and eventually flow through a copper grid covered with a carbon film. The samples were then stained by allowing the grids to float in a 2 wt. % solution of uranyl acetate for 1 minute. The morphology and microstructure of the PLA and BC/PLA composite samples were studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Philips XL30S FEG, NL). Prior to SEM observation, all samples were sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold to avoid electrical charging. The surface properties of the samples were investigated using an attenuated total reflectance-Fourier transform infrared spectroscope (ATR-FTIR, Nicolet 8700, USA). The DSC crystallinity and melting behaviour were studied for neat PLA and for BC/PLA composite samples, using a sample mass between 2 and 5 mg. In order to remove prior thermal history, specimens were initially heated to 200°C at 40°C/min and then held for 5 minutes at 200°C to ensure complete melting. The experimental data were collected for both a cooling scan at 5 °C /min to 20°C and a subsequent heating scan at 5°C /min to 200 °C.

The wettability of the PLA film containing different BC amounts was characterized in terms of the contact angle between water drops and the surface of the modified samples using a contact angle measuring system, G10 (KRUSS). For this purpose, the drops of water were mounted on 3 different areas of the surface with a micro-syringe. The

recorded results are the mean values of three measurements on different parts of the films.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows an electron micrograph of the bacterial cellulose nano-fibres. The freeze-dried BC gel consists of a random assembly of microfibrils and small amounts of cells. Sulphuric acid hydrolysis of the cellulose fibres causes breakdown of the fibres into rod-like fragments. The average diameter and length of individual bacterial cellulose nano-fibres was measured to be 20 nm and 200-500 nm, respectively. Introduction of sulphate groups along the surface of the crystallites during the hydrolysis process results in a negative charge of the surface because the PH value increases, which accounts for the stability of colloidal suspensions of crystallites. Upon drying, the crystalline fragments are rod-like and well dispersed. However, some aggregated nano-fibres were observed, probably due to the formation of hydrogen bonds in the hydroxyl groups.

Figure 1. Transmission electron micrograph of bacterial cellulose nano-fibres by sulphuric acid hydrolysis

Figure 2. Cross section SEM image of pure PLA and PLA/BC (5% wt.)

The SEM surface and cross section of the PLA scaffold and BC/PLA composite scaffold are shown in Figure 2. From the surface morphology shown in Figure 2, it is

apparent that the BC/PLA composite has higher porosity than pure PLA samples. Also, the BC/PLA composite is more interconnected, which facilitates cell attachment and growth.

In order to characterize the chemical structure by identifying the functional groups present in each sample, Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectroscopy was carried out on samples of BC, PLA and BC/PLA composites, as shown in Figure 3. The typical absorption peaks of PLA at 1744 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching), 145 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), 1180 cm^{-1} (C-O and C-O-C stretching) and 1088 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching) are clearly seen in the spectra, in addition to the newly introduced peaks at $(3250-3750)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-OH stretching) and 2894 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), which belong to bacterial cellulose [16-17]. The peaks for the bacterial cellulose are less obvious due to the low content of bacterial cellulose and the limited resolution of the FTIR – ATR.

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of PLA (a), BC (b) and BC/PLA composites with 5% wt.% BC.

Figure 4 illustrates the variations of water uptake gain with time during the water absorption period for the PLA film, the PLA scaffold, and the BC/PLA composite. It is seen that water absorption of the PLA scaffold and the BC/PLA composite increases sharply and remains stable after 40 hr. BC/PLA has the highest water absorption due to the introduction of hydrophilic bacterial cellulose. However, the PLA scaffold shows higher water absorption than that of the PLA film, probably due to its porous structure.

Figure 4. The water uptake of PLA film, PLA scaffold and BC/PLA scaffold

The contact angle formed on the three-phase line of the solid/liquid/gas system, provides a simple and convenient way to evaluate the hydrophilicity and/or hydrophobicity of the films for different BC content. Figure 5 shows the contact angle for samples of PLA and BC/PLA containing different amounts of BC nano-fibres. It is apparent that the wettability of PLA is improved significantly with a content increase from 0 to 5 % wt, when the contact angle decreases to more than 20°. This shows that the hydrophilicity of pure PLA is improved significantly with the addition of even small amounts of bacterial cellulose nano-fibres. Changes of surface morphology also affect the wettability of the film due to introduction of nano-scaled bacterial cellulose.

Figure 6 shows the DSC curve of the original PLA film and the BC/PLA composite. The melting point (T_m) of the BC/PLA, which was measured to be 148.57°C, is a little lower than that of the original PLA film. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the BC/PLA decreased from 63.5 to 60.1°C.

Figure 5. The contact angle variation of PLA films with different BC content

Figure 6. DSC curves of (a) PLA, and (b) BC/PLA composite

CONCLUSIONS

Poly(lactic acid) composite scaffolds show increased surface hydrophilicity, better porous structure and improved thermal properties when reinforced with bacterial cellulose nano-fibres. The mechanical properties, biocompatibility and cell-surface adhesion are also expected to be improved.

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References

1. S. Yang, K. F. Leong, Z. Du, C. K. Chua, The design of scaffolds for use in tissue engineering, part I. Traditional factors. *Tissue Engineering*, 7 (2001) 679-689
2. B. H. Zhao, I. S. Lee, I. H. Han, J. C. Park, S. M. Chung, Effects of surface morphology on human osteosarcoma cell response, *Curr Appl Phys* 7(2007), e6-e10.
3. J. Yang, J. Bei, S. Wang, Enhanced cell affinity of poly (D, L-lactide) by combining plasma treatment with collagen anchorage, *Biomaterials*, 23 (2002) 2607-2614.
4. R. A. Quirk, M. C. Davies, S. J. B. Tendler, K. M. Shakesheff, Surface engineering of poly (lactic acid) by entrapment of modifying species, *Macromolecules*, 33 (2000)258-260.
5. G. Khang, S. J. Lee, J. H. Jeon, J. H. Lee, H. B. Lee, Interaction for fibroblast cell onto physicochemically treated PLGA surfaces, *Polym. Koera* 24 (2000) 869-876
6. Y. S. Nam, J. J. Yoon, J. G. Lee, T. G. Park, Adhesion behaviors of hepatocytes cultured onto biodegradable polymer surface modified by alkali hydrolysis process, *J. Biomat. Sci. Polym. E*, 10 (1999) 1145-1158.
7. T. Naritomi, T. Kouda, H. Yano, F. Yoshinaga. Effect of lactate in bacterial cellulose production from fructose in continuous culture, *J. Ferm. Bioeng.*, 85(1998)89-95.
8. N. Tahara, M. Tabuchi, K. Watanabe, H. Yano, Y. Morinaga, F. Yoshinaga, Degree of polymerization of cellulose from *Acetobacter xylinum* decreased by cellulase produced by the strain. *Biosci. Biotechnol. Biochem.*, 61 (1997)1862-1865.
9. T. Miyamoto, S. Takahashi, H. Ito, H. Inagaki, Y. Noishiki, Tissue biocompatibility of cellulose and its derivatives, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.*, 23 (1989) 125-133.

10. P. Ross, R. Mayer, M. Benziman, Cellulose biosynthesis and function in bacteria, *Microbiol Rev.* 55 (1991) 3 5–58.
11. G. Guhados, W. K. Wan, J. L. Hutter, Measurement of the Elastic Modulus of Single Bacterial Cellulose Fibers Using Atomic Force Microscopy, *Langmuir*, 21 (2005) 6642-6646.
12. M. Shoda, Y. Sugano, Recent advances in bacterial cellulose production, *Biotechnology and Bioprocess Engineering*, 10 (2005) 1-8.
13. D. Klemm, D. Schumann, U. Udhardt, S. Marsch, Bacterial, synthesized cellulose—artificial blood vessels for microsurgery, *Prog. Polym. Sci.*, 26 (2001) 1561–1603.
14. C. H. Tu, Q. Cai, J. Yang, Y. Q. Qan, J. Z. Bei, S. G. Wang, The fabrication and characterization of poly (lactic acid) scaffolds for tissue engineering by improved solid-liquid phase separation, *Polym. Adv. Technol.*, 14(2003) 565-573.
15. Ch. Schugens, V. Maquet, C. Grandfils, R. Jerome, Ph. Teyssie, Biodegradable and macroporous polylactied implants for cell transplantation: 1 Preparation of macroporous polylactied supports by solid-liquid phase separation, *Polymer*, 37 (1996) 1027-1038.
16. T. N. Parakumar, D. Edith, S. J. Luc, *Appl.surf. Sci.*, 253 (2006)278.